

MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR PRODUCING CULTIVATOR PAW PARTS WITH A POWDER SURFACING COATING BY CASTING USING GASIFIED MODELS AND THEIR SUBSEQUENT HEAT TREATMENT

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Abstract. *The article develops modern innovative technologies for the manufacture of chisel paws of cultivators with a wear-resistant powdery sormite coating by casting using gasified models.*

Keywords: *gasification, gasified models, material costs, special platform, foam models.*

Introduction. Gasification pattern casting (GMC) is a method of producing castings that uses a pattern made from a material that is gasified when molten metal is poured into a mold. The most common material for models is polystyrene foam.

Gasification casting as a new technological process appeared in the mid-1950 s. Its main purpose was to improve casting accuracy while significantly reducing equipment and material costs compared to lost wax casting technology.

Today, the method of casting using gasified models is the most acceptable method for producing cast parts for machines for various purposes. For the first time in 1960, A.R.Chudnovsky in the Russian Federation developed a method for producing foam models and producing castings of cast parts using gasified models and introduced them in 1965 at the Gorky Automobile Plant for the production of cast parts for machines and mechanisms (tools, equipment, fixtures) [1,2]. In 1966-67, this technology was well mastered and introduced at the Volzhsky Automobile Plant for the production of die parts, and subsequently at a number of other production enterprises [3,4].

In 1988-1997, this method, according to the project of NPO Tekhnolog, was used at the Tashkent excavator and tool factories for the manufacture of parts for excavator rollers and other tools [5]. After the bankruptcy and liquidation of the factories, to this day the method of casting using gasified models has not been used at any production enterprise in our republic.

Goal of the work. Development and research of the technological process for manufacturing chisel paws of cultivators with a wear-resistant powdered sormite coating by casting on expanded polystyrene gasified models (PPGM), as well as to determine the mechanical properties and structures of steel castings.

This method is a promising environmentally friendly technology for producing castings, which make it possible to obtain high-quality castings with minimal material costs. In the foundry industry, there are a large number of ways to produce cast parts. Gasification casting has the widest innovative potential among foundry technologies [6]. Therefore, casting using gasified models

provides versatility in the designs of (cast iron or steel) castings and the ability to combine several parts into one. LGM allows you to obtain more accurate and smooth castings with smaller allowances for machining. Using modern milling machines, it is possible to produce models from block polystyrene foam without the cost of making expensive model equipment. This is due to the use of dry sand without a binder as a refractory filler, which is strengthened due to a difference in gas pressure at the stage of making the mold and pouring it with metall.

Objects and methods of research. The object of the study is the chisel tines of cultivators with a wear-resistant powdery sormite coating with a layer thickness of 2-3 mm. Currently (since 2008) at the Tashkent enterprise of the Metallmexqurilish Holding Company, a casting site for gasified models has been re-organized. This enterprise has developed and mastered technologies for the production of foam models and castings of cast parts for agricultural, soil-cultivating, earth-moving, energy, metallurgical, mechanical engineering and other machines and mechanisms with wear-resistant carbide sormite coating and without coating [6].

At the foundry shop of Holding Company "Metallmexqurilish" a separate model section with all equipment and instruments (including 4 new workplaces) and a molding section with special foundry flasks (including core materials, quartz sand and a vibrating table), as well as a section for pouring metals into container flasks have been specially organized. In addition, there is a special platform for knocking out, trimming and cleaning workpieces, as well as a tumbling drum for final cleaning of workpieces and cast parts. Some blanks and parts undergo machining and heat treatment at this enterprise to the state of the finished product.

The results obtained and their discussion. Using these technologies, various types of cast parts of machines and equipment with a wear-resistant carbide coating with a layer thickness from 2.0 to 4.0 mm and without coating were manufactured by casting using gasified models from 35GL steel. For example, chisel paws of cultivators with a wear-resistant powdered sormite coating (fig.1, a, b, c, d) [7].

The main feature of this method is the use of a model that cannot be removed before pouring metal into the container flasks, which determines its main advantages:

- granular compositions of expanded polystyrene meet all the requirements of the technical specifications;
- special foundry gasified polystyrene foam foams well;
- a high-quality foam model of the product is obtained using a mold;
- the accuracy of casting parts is increased due to the one-piece mold, the absence of the operation of extracting the model, the displacement of half-molds and cores during assembly, which makes it possible to reduce allowances for machining or without it;
- using these technologies, it is possible to produce castings of parts of simple or complex configurations without the use of cores, since molding is carried out according to a clean model;
- the process of manufacturing a casting mold is simplified, there is no need to use detachable parts and cores;
- high-quality castings of parts are obtained when molding a flask-container with dry quartz sand;
- the labor intensity of cutting and cleaning of casting parts is reduced due to the absence of fills and burrs that appear on the castings due to the mold parting and the use of cores;
- the quality of casting parts with a wear-resistant carbide coating obtained by casting using gasified models is improved;

- the scope and possibilities of automation and mechanization of the processes of manufacturing castings of machine parts and mechanisms are expanding;
- the area of widespread use of PPGM technology is expanding.

The above-mentioned advantages of the method make it possible to sharply shorten the production cycle, reduce the labor intensity of producing a foam model and obtaining castings of parts. Therefore, the method of casting polystyrene foam gasified models began to quickly develop, expand and be introduced into production.

Fig.1. Foam models and cast parts for chisel paws of cultivators with wear-resistant carbide coating: a-foam model; b-foam model with coating on the main wearing surfaces; c-foam model over the entire wearing surface coating; d-cast steel part of the cultivator's feet with a carbide coating and after thermal hardening.

Conclusions. Currently, at the model site of the Metallmexqurilish JSC enterprise, various types of foam models and castings of parts with a hard-alloy sormite coating are produced by casting using gasified models, using new developed technologies. Of these, many cast parts are subjected to heat treatment with double phase recrystallization [7]. Optimal heat treatment modes (hardening and tempering) for these parts are carried out at a heating temperature of 925°S - 1150°S , followed by tempering at 300°S - 600°S . After heat treatment, the wear resistance of cast parts increases 3-4 times higher than that of serial products [6-8]. This innovative technology has been introduced into JSC “Metallmexqurilish” with an economic effect.

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